

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE MASS MEDIA IN
IMPROVING SOCIETY'S LITERACY

Ahmadjonova Gulchehra Shavkat qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

gulchehraahmadjonova462@gmail.com

Abstract: This article talks about the role of the mass media in today's developing era and the role and importance of the mass media in shaping the society's spirituality and political thinking, as well as about the effective reforms that are being implemented in the world and our republic in.

Key words: information, mass media, media space, mass culture, information code, internet, information and communication technologies.

New information technologies, and especially the Internet, have created a new situation on a global scale. Journalism began to influence qualitatively renewed relations between individuals, society and the state. The concept of "Global Village", figuratively expressed by Professor Marshall McLuhan of the University of Toronto in the 60s of the last century, continues to become a reality. Today, all humanity is compacting to the size of a community. Instead of industrial society, the role of mass communications and information has increased immeasurably.

During the years of independence, the legal, social, political and economic conditions necessary for the activity of free mass media were formed. Reforms aimed at developing mass media as an institution of civil society continue consistently. The important thing to note is that the public realized that it is impossible to build a civil society and ensure human freedom and rights without developing free mass media.

The recent emergence of new electronic mass media is a sign that the information field is developing rapidly. Ensuring citizens' right to reliable information is the duty of the mass media, a fundamental principle of democratic government. In Uzbekistan, the mass media serve as a platform for the delivery of such information and play an important role in effective cooperation between the government and the public.

The activity and number of mass media during the years of independence of Uzbekistan has been developing widely in the following years. In particular, according to the statistics of October 1, 2022, "the number of mass media in the national information space is 1,962, and the number of Internet publications is 733"¹. Another piece of information is that if in 2019 the number of sources of information services in state and non-state organizations - official websites, channels on social networks - was 559, then in 2021 this number reached 2410. As of October 1, 2022, the population of our country was 35.8 million people, and 24.7 million people over the age of 15 were

able to actively exercise public control. , per capita, these numbers are very low. Today, through mass media or social networks, it is easy to rely on the national idea for the problem of the people, the country's perspective in the philosophical thinking of the society, to ensure the freedom of speech, to see the result of the solution of ideas in real life within the philosophical thinking of every citizen.

Considering that the issue of ensuring freedom of speech and the press occupies a special place in the development of civil society, First President Islam Karimov says: "The most important priority in terms of further development and qualitative renewal of our society is the protection of human rights and freedoms, It is correct in all respects to say that democratic principles that ensure freedom of speech and press, as well as transparency, and the openness of reforms in society, are implemented not in words or on paper, but in practical life.

The achievement of independence of our country initiated a new stage in the liberalization of the information sphere and the provision of freedom of speech. Over the past years, extensive reforms and many measures have been implemented in this area. In this regard, it is necessary to note that an excellent legal framework has been created for the activity of information media and that it plays an important role in ensuring the freedom and rights of people in the field of receiving information.

He started the next stage of national development. Young people are the priceless wealth of our nation and state. All conditions are created for them, the door of opportunities is wide open. The decree of the head of our state on July 5, 2017 "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" brought the work in this regard to a new stage. The large-scale reforms that are being carried out are primarily aimed at forming a healthy world view of Uzbekistan's youth. On the way to this goal, it is necessary for the state and society to create ample opportunities and provide all-round support for each young person to set great goals for themselves and achieve them. This expresses the urgency of the issue by demanding to be more responsible and not indifferent to the education of the young generation. Significant work has been done in our country to ensure freedom of speech, to reorganize the management system of the information and mass communications sector, and to increase the role of mass media in solving the problematic issues of socio-political and socio-economic development.

At the same time, the analysis of the current situation in the field shows that the challenges arising in the media space are not being responded to quickly and appropriately, and the society's needs for timely provision of comprehensive information about the large-scale reforms being implemented in the country. requires a

significant increase in the work in the field of information services of state bodies and organizations, bringing the activities of mass media to a new level in terms of quality.

Young people are the priceless wealth of our nation and state. All conditions are created for them, the door of opportunities is wide open. The decree of the head of our state on July 5, 2017 "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" brought the work in this regard to a new stage. The large-scale reforms that are being carried out are primarily aimed at forming a healthy world view of Uzbekistan's youth. On the way to this goal, it is necessary for the state and society to create ample opportunities and provide all-round support for each young person to set great goals for themselves and achieve them. This expresses the urgency of the issue by demanding to be more responsible and not indifferent to the education of the young generation.

To improve the effectiveness of information delivery aimed at improving the image of our country in the world community, to regularly publish articles in the international mass media and in the international media space, to promote the country's achievements to the general public, regularly hold briefings, roundtables, conferences, in the international space. Tasks such as periodic publication of detailed author's materials about Uzbekistan with foreign mass media promoting a positive image of Uzbekistan are set to be implemented in 2022-2026 according to the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan"

REFERENCES

1. <https://hozir.org/ozbekiston-respublirasi-oliy-va-orta-maxsus-talim-vazirligi-mu.html?page=25>
2. <https://bestpublication.org/index.php/ozf/article/download/6207/6545/5827>
3. <https://azkurs.org/ozbekistonda-ommaviy-axborot-vositalarining-jamiyatda-orni.html>
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ommaviy-axborot-vositalarining-jamiyat-taraqqiyotidagi-o-rni-va-ahamiyati>
5. https://www.samdu.uz/upload/content-files/%D0%90%D0%B2%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B5%D1%84%D0%B5%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%82_%D0%91%D0%90%D0%A5%D0%9E%D0%94%D0%98%D0%A0_%D0%AD%D1%88%D0%B1%D0%B5%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%B2.pdf
6. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4390513>